

Recep Pasha Mosque in Rhodes

also known as “Recep Paşa Camii”

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Tomb, Aegean, Religious Place, Turkic, Language, Islamic Traditions, Sunni, Hanafi

The Recep Pasha Mosque in the walled city of Rhodes was built in 1588 at the behest of Recep Pasha, an Ottoman statesman who later became Grand Vizier in 1632. The square, single-domed mosque, decorated on the interior with Iznik tiles, is oriented toward the qibla, and is attached to a three-domed portico. The türbe (mausoleum) of Recep Pasha is located to the east of the mosque. There is a shadirvan (octagonal fountain) located to the northwest of the mosque, in front of the entrance. In 1671, Evliya Çelebi described the mosque during his travels in Rhodes, commenting on the beauty of its decoration. The mosque had been financed by a vakf (Islamic charitable foundation) since its creation; during the Italian administration of the Dodecanese between 1912 and 1943, this foundation came under the authority of the Italian administration. Since 1947, when the Dodecanese were incorporated into Greece, the vakfs of Rhodes and neighboring Kos have been administered by committees appointed by the Greek government. Suggestions have been made that the mosque be converted into a museum of Islamic art and/or ceramics. Currently (as of 2020), the mosque is not open for visit or worship, and has been closed for the past 25 years.

Date Range: 1588 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Recep Pasha Mosque in Rhodes

Region tags: Greece, Aegean, Dodecanese, Rhodes

The Recep Pasha Mosque in the old city of Rhodes, with associated türbe and shadirvan.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Evliya Çelebi, *Evliya Çelebi Seyahatnamesi*, Kitap 9 Cilt 1, trans. Seyit Ali Kahraman, 2010, pp. 257 - 274.
- Source 2: Evliya Çelebi, *Evliya Çelebi Seyahatnamesi*, Vol. IX, transcribed by Yücel Dağlı, Seyit Ali Kahraman, Robert Dankoff, 2005, pp. 105-139.

Notes: Editions of Evliya Çelebi's travel to Rhodes are available in both Modern Turkish (Kahraman) and transcription of Ottoman Turkish (Dağlı et al.)

- Source 1: Gross, Andreas. The situation of the inhabitants of Rhodes and Kos with a Turkish cultural

background. Committee on Legal Affairs and Human Rights, Council of Europe, 2011.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <http://tourism.rhodes.gr/?p=9244&lang=en>

– Source 1 Description: This is the online guide of the Municipality of Rhodes

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.aa.com.tr/en/europe/greece-turns-spiritual-center-of-muslim-turks-on-rhodes-island-into-music-faculty/2719657>

– Source 1 Description: The site of the Reçep Paşa Project, which describes recent partial collapse (2011) and efforts to turn building into a museum.

– Source 1 URL: https://www.mfa.gov.tr/no_309_-23-aralik-2011_-yunanistan_daki-recep-pasa-camii-hk_.tr.mfa

– Source 1 Description: This is a statement from the Turkish Ministry of Foreign Affairs in 2011 regarding the collapse of the portico of the Recep Pasha Mosque.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: None

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

Notes: Today, there is a wall and fence separating the mosque and immediate area from the surrounding Old Town of Rhodes.

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Square

Notes: Mosque: square floor plan, with circular dome.

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

–Other [specify]: Octagonal

Notes: Türbe (mausoleum)

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

–Other [specify]: Octagonal

Notes: Shadirvan (fountain).

↳ One single feature

–Other [specify]: None

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Field doesn't know

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

– Individual

– Social

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

Notes: The mosque is currently in need of conservation (as of 2020), but still standing.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Other [specify]: Octagonal

Notes: Shadirvan (fountain)

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The mosque likely predates the associated türbe (mausoleum).

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: God (monotheistic)

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:
– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:
– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:
A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.
– No

Notes: The mosque was commissioned by an individual, Recep Pasha, an Ottoman statesman.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:
– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:
– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:
– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:
– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:
– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:
– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:
– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:
– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:
– No

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:
– Yes

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth
– No

↳ Sand
– No

↳ Clay
– Yes

Notes: Glazed tiles decorate the interior.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Wood
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other
–Other [specify]: Lead

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

Notes: Today (2023), it is not possible to view the interior decoration of the mosque, as the mosque is closed to the public; during its usage, interior decoration was visible to the visitor.

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The plaque above the entrance to the mosque and geometric decorations around the entrance are carved in relief.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: None.

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: Traces of red paint around entrance on exterior

– Yes [specify]: Glazed tiles

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: The türbe associated with the mosque is a funerary structure.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Türbe (mausoleum)

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: While a supreme high god is worshipped, the deity is not considered to be physically manifested ("present") within the mosque.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A.

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Angels and occasionally djinn might be considered to be present.

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

Notes: Angels and/or djinn may have been considered to communicate with some humans at this site.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A.

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Some visitors may have communicated with angels and/or djinn at this site.

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: 50-200

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Small-scale rituals in the form of the five daily prayers took place daily.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Notes: Praying in community (at a mosque) was obligatory for men on Fridays, but women could pray either in community or alone.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Field doesn't know

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Notes: The celebration of Eid ul-Adha and Eid ul-Fitr took place throughout the city, but the mosque was used for prayer during these holidays.

↳ Frequency of festivals

–specify: There are two major holidays per year: Eid ul-Adha and Eid ul-Fitr.

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

–Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Generally, Muslim members of society participated in Muslim holidays.

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: 50-250

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

– Non-elites

Notes: Food consumption was not limited to certain members of the population.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Notes: A sheikh would typically have been associated with the mosque and led Friday prayers.

↳ Present full time

– No

↳ Present part time

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Notes: While the sheikh typically led Friday prayers, other male members of the congregation could lead prayers within the mosque as well.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Today, the mosque's outlying structures do not include living quarters for a sheikh.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– No

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– Yes

Notes: Fountains are associated with the mosque.

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Notes: While common Islamic religious texts such as the Quran and other religious texts were read and recited at this location, no original or unusual religious texts are associated with this location.

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Recep Pasha Mosque in Rhodes, Evliya. Evliya çelebi seyahatnamesi. Translated by Seyit Ali Kahraman. Vol. 9/1. Yapı Kredi Yayınları, 2010pp. 257-274.

Reference: Recep Pasha Mosque in Rhodes, Evliya. Evliya Çelebi, Evliya Çelebi Seyahatnamesi, Vol. IX. Translated by Yücel Dağlı, Seyit Ali Kahraman, and Robert Dankoff, 2005.

Reference: Recep Pasha Mosque in Rhodes, Gross, Andreas. "The Situation of the Inhabitants of Rhodes and Kos with a Turkish Cultural Background". Committee on Legal Affairs and Human Rights, Council of Europe, 2011.